

Annual Report for May 1, 2022-April 30, 2023

RCD Nexus

NSF CI CoE: Demo Pilot: Advancing Research Computing and Data: Strategic Tools, Practices, and Professional Development

[NSF Grant OAC-2100003](#)

May 1, 2022-April 30, 2023

For Public Distribution

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About the RCD Nexus

The RCD Nexus is funded by NSF's Office of Advanced Cyberinfrastructure as an NSF Cyberinfrastructure Center of Excellence (CI CoE) demo pilot. It is a Research Computing and Data (RCD) Resource and Career Center that creates tools, practices, and professional development resources to support individuals and institutions. RCD Nexus both leverages and augments the infrastructure of the Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC) in order to reach, support, and engage with Research Computing and Data and other related professionals. CaRCC is uniquely positioned to support and grow the RCD community, with a vision to advance the frontiers of research by improving the effectiveness of RCD professionals and organizations. The CaRCC community is growing rapidly, with People Network membership increasing by more than 150% per year. Activities are expanding, including multiple new working- and interest- groups, as well as increasing partnerships with other RCD partners.

CaRCC's People Network and groups help RCD Nexus reach its intended audience, and the RCD Nexus has, in turn, helped the People Network and CaRCC expand rapidly, both in numbers and scope. With CaRCC's rapid growth, it has become increasingly difficult for it to be managed and overseen by volunteers alone. RCD Nexus has thus filled a critical role by providing central staff and resources to ensure organization, consistency, and professionalism as CaRCC progresses toward becoming a more formal professional society. RCD Nexus-funded staff are largely leading the general administration, management, communications, and engagement efforts – which allows CaRCC volunteers and members to focus on sharing their RCD-related knowledge.

The main areas of emphasis for the RCD Nexus include:

- A more robust and sustainable implementation of the RCD Capabilities Model and a new Community Dataset portal
- Conducting an RCD Professional Staffing Survey and sharing the results
- Advancing the adoption of the Human Resources (HR) Job Family Framework
- Developing a Career Arcs resource for RCD professionals
- Curating leading practices for staff professional development, and for involving students in RCD workforce development

For information about the RCD Nexus, please visit the project website: <http://rcd-nexus.org>.

About This Report

This report represents the project year of NSF grant OAC-210003 from May 1, 2022 to April 30, 2023.

Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation.

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For updates to this report and other reports from the RCD Nexus, please visit <http://rcd-nexus.org>.

Executive Summary

RCD Nexus both leverages and augments the Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC) in order to reach, support, and engage with Research Computing and Data professionals. With CaRCC's rapid growth, it has become increasingly difficult to manage by volunteers alone. RCD Nexus has filled a critical role by providing central staff, leadership, and resources as CaRCC progresses toward becoming a professional society. Highlights for the reporting period fall into the following categories:

Communications and Engagement – We developed a communications plan for RCD Nexus, along with brand and style guides, and adopted a new Constituent Relationship Management (CRM) software platform to centralize communications, list management, and prepare for the future possibility of charging membership fees. We led several events during the reporting period, including the CaRCC Annual Retreat, and RCD Nexus Day, which brought together more than 80 RCD professionals during the PEARC22 conference.

Developing Career Arcs – We gathered example career-arc narratives from existing resources, such as Women in HPC (WHPC) and designed and distributed an online survey of factors that influence RCD career choices. We presented our analysis of factors that influence RCD career decisions at the PEARC22 conference. This paper won *Best Paper, Workforce Development, Training, Diversity, and Education*, as well as the *Phil Andrews Award*, granted to a manuscript deemed to be the most impactful in practice of research computing.

RCD Capabilities Model – We continued development of a more robust and sustainable implementation of the RCD Capabilities Model and an associated data-exploration portal. We made significant progress toward a Version 2.0 of the Model, and identified the need for a more streamlined version for emerging and under-resourced programs. We created a new Focused Tools committee to focus on the latter. We continued consulting with the American Indian Higher Education Consortium in support of their Cyberinfrastructure Strategic Planning (CISP) Initiative (AIHEC), and continued to support the EPSCoR CI Workshop project¹ with data and analysis including the report “A Baseline of EPSCoR Research CI Capabilities”, and the associated workshop at the [27th NSF EPSCoR National Conference](#).

RCD Staff Resources – At RCD Nexus Day in July 2022, the staff workforce development workstream held a workshop with outcomes that included a set of priorities to guide the work we have been doing during this reporting period:

- Obtaining information about successful student programs
- Learning about resources for mentor development

¹ NSF (OIA) Award 2033483, Award 2033519, and Award 2033514, Collaborative Research: “Building Research Cyberinfrastructure in EPSCoR Jurisdictions: Assessment, Planning and Partnerships”

- Gathering ideas for establishing funding sustainability

We have established a CaRCC interest group of 60 members from diverse institutions that meets bi-monthly and is gathering resource materials for RCD staff workforce development. We also established a standing committee that will gather and curate institutional RCD program stories for eventual deposit into a repository in the RCD Nexus portal.

Student Workforce Development – We explored existing models for student RCD workforce development at both the undergraduate and graduate levels. We hosted a one-day workshop in conjunction with RCD Nexus Day and PEARC22 during which leaders from across the RCD community identified three top priorities:

- Finding successful student workforce development programs to serve as models
- Developing mentoring resources
- Resources for funding and sustainability

We chartered a 61-member Student Workforce Development interest group that is developing a guide sharing leading practices and models from organizations who are doing this successfully.

Job Family Matrix Adoption – Interest in the HR Job Family Matrix remains high. To date there have been 301 total downloads from 251 unique emails across 153 different institutions, including 99 downloads from the past year. To assist RCD hiring managers with implementation, we conducted a series of interviews with institutions that have completed the process. Findings from these Q & A sessions have been summarized thus far, and the creation of a guidebook is underway.

RCD Workforce Survey – We continued processing the data from the 2021 workforce survey, publishing a public data resource on the RCD Nexus data portal, and will soon present a peer-reviewed journal article at the PEARC23 conference that focuses on compensation for RCD professionals.

Program Administration – In addition to the managing contracts and overseeing spending, some program administration highlights include: Coordinating the May 2022 CaRCC Annual retreat, holding the first annual RCD Nexus Day co-located with PEARC22 and RCD Nexus staff lead and contribute to the CaRCC Chairs, Engagement, and Logistics operations groups.

Looking Forward – The growth and the reputation of CaRCC and RCD Nexus for delivering results has led to increased requests for support and resources. This growth has also led to a greater need for core resources that enable and coordinate volunteers, and reach out to more communities to broaden the representation within CaRCC. Short and long term priorities include expanding our work in the core areas of tools, leading practices, and curated training resources, ensuring these are highly visible and accessible. We will also coordinate the development of a model for an RCD professional society.

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1 Communications and Engagement

In summer of 2022 we developed a general communications plan related to RCD Nexus. The plan included:

- Developing a brand/style guide for RCD Nexus that leveraged the existing, well-established CaRCC brand in order to give RCD Nexus a wide audience and credibility. (Completed in Summer 2022.)
- Creating a LinkedIn presence to communicate with a broader audience about RCD Nexus and CaRCC tools and activities (Ongoing.)
- Selecting and integrating a cloud-based Constituent Relationship Management (CRM) software tool that (more on this below.)
- Identifying (in partnership with the CaRCC Engagement group) a set of annual events on which to focus our main communication efforts. (Ongoing)
- Development of a suite of standard communications products including brochures, and other printed materials for events, as well as a new external electronic newsletter using the CRM. (Ongoing)
- Updating the CaRCC and RCD Nexus websites with a more modern template, and more user-friendly content and interface. (Began this effort in March, 2023)

Selected and integrated Constituent Relationship Management (CRM) software

As CaRCC membership and activity continues to grow rapidly, one challenge that had to be addressed was how best to manage membership lists, keep track of those activities, and communicate most efficiently and effectively with our target audiences. Although CaRCC has been quite successful at remaining organized as it grew using traditional spreadsheets and shared documents, the organization has grown to a size and complexity that we determined it would benefit from a CRM system. During the reporting period, we researched various products and ultimately selected a product called Wild Apricot that was developed specifically for small and mid-sized nonprofit membership and volunteer organizations. In the first quarter of 2023, we have been testing the product and setting up integrations with our other software products. We will be presenting it to the larger CaRCC community at the upcoming Annual Retreat in June and rolling it out for use in late summer.

The tool will allow us to maintain cross-referenced membership and volunteer databases that track individuals' specific subject-matter interests, use of RCD Nexus tools and resources, volunteer activities, involvement with CaRCC groups, and attendance at CaRCC/RCD Nexus events. This information will enable more effective, targeted communication campaigns to our members and others in the RCD community, more effectively identify and recruit potential volunteers for CaRCC and RCD Nexus efforts, and work to ensure the RCD community remains well informed of the RCD Nexus tools and resources available to them.

Other things the tool will enable include:

- Event management and ticketing
- Group membership and volunteer opportunity signup
- Targeted, efficient, and effective communications with newsletter and email templates and metrics on readership, open rates, etc.
- Central, standardized list and information management across the entire CaRCC organization
- Potential for managing paid memberships, or various membership types, should CaRCC decide to begin charging for some services.

Engagement efforts and events

During the reporting period, the CaRCC Engagement working group, under the leadership of RCD Nexus lead, Claire Mizumoto, worked to transition its previous communications work to Daphne McCanse so it could spend more time on engagement and recruitment activities. The group enabled the continued rapid growth of the People Network through leadership, membership drives, and identifying opportunities for in-person outreach through events.

Some specific efforts during the period include:

- “Bring Your Colleague to CaRCC” recruitment effort that encouraged existing members to invite their colleagues to join the People Network and/or attend working or interest group calls
- Identified and researched a list of RCD conferences and events where CaRCC/RCD Nexus may want to cultivate a sustained outreach and engagement presence through presentations, booths, etc. in order to reach new members, particularly those in traditionally underserved communities
- Developed a [Wall of Thanks](#) - appreciation page for CaRCC volunteers

Blog posts - RCD Nexus produced the following blog posts, in addition to the monthly posts announcing all the People Network and related sessions.

- May 25, 2022: 2021 RCD Capabilities Model Community Data report now available ([link](#), also posted on [Internet2 blog](#))
- June 14, 2022: PEARC21 report: Building a shared RCD community resource ([link](#))
- June 18, 2022: 2022 RCD Capabilities Model Office Hours ([link](#))
- June 21, 2022: Certified Cyberinfrastructure Facilitator Training and Development (CCIFTD) BoF at PEARC22 ([link](#))
- July 6, 2022: CaRCC at PEARC22! ([link](#))
- Sept 12, 2022: Who We (RCD Professionals) Are ([link](#) and [link to visualizations](#))
- Sept 19, 2022: Career Arcs paper wins Phil Andrews award at PEARC22! ([link](#))
- Oct 3, 2022: Understanding the CaRCC Facings ([link](#))

- Oct 18, 2022: Help spread the word: 2022 Capabilities Model Assessment — Due December 15 ([link](#), also posted on [Internet2 bog](#))
- Dec 7, 2022: Make the list! Submit your RCD Capabilities Model Assessment by December 15 ([link](#))
- Jan 9, 2023: CaRCC/RCD Nexus 2022 Retrospective ([link](#), also posted on [Internet2 blog](#))
- Jan 27, 2023: Nexus Day Staff and Student Workforce Development Update ([link](#))
- March 16, 2023: Register now! Free Virtual Residency Workshop on Research Computing ([link](#), also posted on [Internet2 blog](#))
- March 22, 2023: 2023 RCD Capabilities Model Office Hours ([link](#))
- March 22, 2023: How long does it take to complete the RCD Capabilities Model? ([link](#))
- March 28, 2023: Student Workforce Development & Internship Survey — Please participate! ([link](#))

RCD professional events

During the reporting period, RCD Nexus held several successful events, bringing together members of the RCD community – from top executive leaders, to those just beginning their RCD careers. These events served both to strengthen and grow professional relationships within the community, and also to communicate, discuss, and improve the products and tools being developed as part of the RCD Nexus project.

CaRCC Annual Retreat – This meeting brings together CaRCC chairs of working, interest, and operations groups, the People Network co-chairs and track coordinators, the CaRCC and RCD Nexus Advisory committees, and others from the broader community (e.g., leaders from Campus Champions, EDUCAUSE, US-RSE) to review activities, determine future activities, and set strategic priorities. The May 2022 meeting included 42 participants and included far forward looking sessions on world building facilitated by Joel Cutcher-Gershenfeld. These dialogues influence how we navigate the growth of CaRCC and the RCD profession broadly.

RCD Nexus Day – This one-day workshop was held as an official co-located event with the PEARC22 conference in July, 2022. It brought together more than 80 RCD professionals from across the U.S. to discuss topics related to RCD staff workforce development and creating and supporting a stronger student pipeline into the RCD profession. The workshop also explored creating a more streamlined version of the RCD Capabilities model for smaller, less complex organizations. Discussions at RCD Nexus Day led to the creation of a Capabilities Model Focused Tools Committee and the RCD Student and Staff Workforce Interest Groups.

New Strategy and Policy-Facing Track

The CaRCC People Network had long planned a track that would focus on Strategy and Policy Facing roles and their interests, and the community had repeatedly expressed interest in having such a track, but there were no new volunteers willing to take on the task of bootstrapping this

work. RCD Nexus staff responded by organizing a steering committee and recruiting a community co-coordinator who could grow into a coordinating role over time. The track launched in late 2022, and has grown rapidly to over 280 subscribers as of April 2023. The first five sessions recorded and shared on the CaRCC youtube channel (www.youtube.com/carcc) have already had over 200 views². Discussion topics have ranged from shared updates and impressions from community meetings (e.g., CASC and the NSF Cybersecurity Summit) to an exploration of factors that impact RCD strategy at different types of institutions.

2 Developing Career Arcs

RCD Nexus is developing a model of Career Arcs for RCD Professionals to explain RCD career options and help existing RCD professionals pursue professional development and advancement.

Our key objectives are to address the following set of challenges, as identified in a series of workshops and meetings:

- Managers need better resources and the ability to offer defined career paths, so their staff are not forced to seek growth opportunities outside the RCD profession.
- Many RCD professionals say they see no clear path for career advancement; this is especially so for data-centric and researcher-facing roles.
- There is a national shortage of RCD (CI) personnel and high employee turnover, with significant training needed to orient new employees.
- There is no formal talent pipeline seeking to join the RCD field. Students who are studying in relevant programs do not have an easy way to learn about or enter the field.
- RCD personnel experience precarious employment with few opportunities for advancement.

We began developing a framework for describing the roles and career arcs of RCD professionals and distributed content through community engagement. Specific activities included:

- Gathering example career-arc narratives from existing resources, such as Women in HPC (WHPC)
- Designing and running an online survey of factors that influence career choices among RCD professionals
- Preparing for a series of in-depth interviews of RCD professionals to better understand their choices, motivations, and the factors that enable success

² See <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLV-SC0CHLTwcsREvcrk7S37iLPPX0rI2t>

Best Paper and Phil Andrews Awards at PEARC22

We presented our analysis of factors that influence RCD career decisions (based upon the survey we conducted in the previous reporting period) at the PEARC22 conference in summer 2022. This paper won *Best Paper, Workforce Development, Training, Diversity, and Education*, as well as the *Phil Andrews Award*, granted to a manuscript deemed to be the most impactful in practice of research computing (See section 10, Chaudhry, S. et al). We did an additional presentation of this material at the [US-RSE Virtual Workshop](#) in the fall. We refined the interview protocol for our in-depth interviews of community members, and have Institutional Review Board (IRB) approvals for several team members (with others now working through their respective IRB processes to be additional interviewers). Interviews are beginning this spring, and will continue at least into the summer. We have a growing list of volunteers to be interviewed, and will be soliciting more this spring and summer.

Once we have gathered interview data, we will synthesize results into personas that represent typical experiences across the community, and will write up narratives for each persona. Each will be enriched with anonymized quotes, to make them personal without identifying real individuals. We will also develop a visualization of career arcs and pathways. We will either hold a workshop or a series of community outreach sessions to get feedback on the materials we develop and gather additional use-cases and data to supplement the personas and visualization. We will then produce a companion paper to the visualization with recommended practices for hiring managers for both recruitment as well as retention of RCD professional staff. Much of this activity will be conducted in collaboration with the Staff and Student Workforce Development workstreams.

3 RCD Capabilities Model

The goal of the RCD Capabilities Model (RCD CM) workstream is to develop a more robust and sustainable implementation of the RCD Capabilities Model assessment tool and an associated data-exploration portal that eliminates the need to create a host of individual reports by hand.

We originally had two broad objectives for the RCD CM workstream:

- Implement a 2.0 version of the RCD Capabilities Model assessment tool and data exploration portal
- Expand consulting and support services to ensure a broad range of institutions can use the model and incorporate it into strategic planning work for their respective RCD programs

We originally intended to implement the 2.0 version of the assessment tool on an existing platform, but as we explored candidate platforms it became clear that they lacked necessary

functionality. We considered continued use of the prototype implementation (augmented with improved help support), but in the course of design and implementation for the data portal an approach emerged to build a web application that would provide a much better user experience, superior integration of assessment data with the new portal, and without excessive development cost. We resolved to follow this approach and our progress makes us confident that this was a good choice.

We heard from a number of smaller or under-resourced institutions and emerging RCD programs that they found the existing RCD Capabilities Model a bit overwhelming, and/or that they lack the resources to complete that level of assessment. In response to this community feedback, the RCD Capabilities Model working group at CaRCC added an additional objective to better meet the needs of these smaller institutions and emerging RCD programs by developing a set of focused tools that helps them identify necessary elements to bootstrap an RCD support program (this activity is described below).

During the development phase for the new portal, we have continued our support for the prototype implementation of the RCD Capabilities Model assessment tool and the annual community datasets derived from contributed assessments. Institutions continue to conduct assessments and get benchmarking reports. A total of 168 institutions have requested copies of the RCD Capabilities Model assessment tool for evaluation, representing all 50 US States, two territories and the District of Columbia, five Canadian provinces, and several other countries outside North America. Since our launch about three years ago, 56 institutions have completed and contributed 81 assessments (some choose to repeat the assessment to provide longitudinal data), representing 32 US States and one US Territory (including 12 EPSCoR jurisdictions), and two Canadian Provinces.

Highlights of our continuing work with the prototype implementation include:

- Published an analysis of the 2021 community dataset, and provided benchmarking reports as well as an anonymized version of the dataset (under DUA) to contributing institutions.
- Conducted a workshop at PEARC22 on “Building and Selling a Strategic Plan for your Research Computing and Data Program” (see Section 10).
- Completed the 2022 RCD CM community dataset campaign, including office hours support, individual outreach and support to institutions conducting assessments, and regular communications to the community to promote the effort. In response to community feedback, we switched to a calendar year period for the annual datasets.
- Aggregated the resulting 2022 data with that of the previous two years and completed initial analysis, including visualizations of summary data and comparisons across

demographic slices. We are currently working on the full community data report (combining years 2020 through 2022).

- Continued our support of the EPSCoR CI Workshop project³ with data and analysis including the report “A Baseline of EPSCoR Research CI Capabilities”, and participated in the associated workshop at the 27th NSF EPSCoR National Conference.

Platform and web application development

We have made good progress on the Implementation of Version 2.0 of the RCD Capabilities Model tools, including:

- Designed and implemented the main web application stack for the assessment tool, leveraging current leading practice modules, platform elements, and automated deployment infrastructure to simplify ongoing support and maintenance.
- Conducted a user-centered design (UCD) review among existing users to evaluate the effectiveness of the assessment tool user model and the interface elements. An analysis of the results of the UCD review informs the design of the v2.0 interface.
- Defined and implemented the database schema for the assessment tool and completed import of the aggregated dataset.
- Completed an integration with CILogon to allow users to login with institutional credentials or (for those who need it) other identity providers including ORCID, Google, Microsoft, etc.
- Made progress developing the interface for the web application and are working toward an alpha version for in-house testing in the next month or so.

We also made good progress on the Implementation of the new data portal, but experienced a setback when a key UX developer was not able to continue with the project. We reprioritized development resources to focus on the assessment tool so institutions could complete 2023 assessments with the new tool. Once we launch that, we will resume work on the data exploration portal. Work completed before we made this shift includes:

- Designed and implemented the main web application stack for the portal, leveraging current leading practice modules, platform elements, and automated deployment infrastructure to simplify ongoing support and maintenance. This work shares much of the same infrastructure used for the assessment tool implementation, and is intended to form the basis for additional web applications (e.g., to explore workforce survey data) in future.
- Conducted a user-centered design analysis of desired functionality for the data exploration portal to shape the functionality for this new set of tools. This work

³ NSF (OIA) Award 2033483, Award 2033519, and Award 2033514, Collaborative Research: “Building Research Cyberinfrastructure in EPSCoR Jurisdictions: Assessment, Planning and Partnerships”

benefited from a collaboration with the User Experience team at the Science Gateways Community Institute (SGCI)⁴.

- Defined the requirements for the web services API that will support the data exploration web application, and completed some of the basic API implementations.

The main work remaining on the exploration portal is the development of visualization tools and an associated query user interface allowing users to select subsets of data and see and download graphic visualizations of this data, using various “lenses” (models for comparison).

Focused Tools work

A new Focused Tools committee with the RCD Capabilities Model working group is working to clarify the requirements and develop tools that help institutions identify necessary elements to bootstrap an RCD support program. The committee was formed early in 2022, and held two focus groups in the Spring of 2022, in partnership with Edge (njedge.net) and the Great Plains Network (greatplains.net) respectively. These workshops gathered representatives from smaller and emerging programs as well as other community members who were interested in supporting this work. The output from the focus groups included several proposed activities that were documented and shaped the agenda for a workshop that was held at the 2022 RCD Nexus Day held in conjunction with PEARC22 in Boston. In response to the feedback received from the community, the committee is now working on two threads of activity:

1. An interview template (and resource list) that can be used to engage with programs that are just getting started with RCD support and “don’t know what they don’t know”
2. An alternate way of working with the existing assessment tool (i.e., with the *new implementation* of the assessment tool) that will allow institutions to focus on selected areas of capabilities, to “chart their own journey” through the model

These new tools will allow the RCD Capabilities Model to be more inclusive and respond to a broader range of institutions. Together with the full assessment and data portal, they will constitute a suite of coordinated tools that respond to the needs of RCD programs from inception through maturity.

Engagement with American Indian Higher Education Consortium

We continue to use a small amount of our consulting resources in an engagement with the American Indian Higher Education Consortium (AIHEC, <http://www.aihec.org/>) in support of their Cyberinfrastructure Strategic Planning (CISP) Initiative. The AIHEC Cyberinfrastructure (CI) Team advances the STEM and education programs at the nation’s 37 Tribal College and Universities (TCUs) by implementing a comprehensive CI capacity-building strategy focusing on

⁴ NSF (OAC) Award 1547611 “S2I2: Impl: The Science Gateways Community Institute (SGCI) for the Democratization and Acceleration of Science”

the colleges' STEM faculty and CI support staff. With support from external partners and regional institutions, this comprehensive CI strategy focuses on CI training, planning, and community-building involving both STEM faculty and TCU IT organizations, providing the resources, technical assistance and national network to advance participating TCUs toward CI-readiness and CI-enabled STEM research and education programs. We are engaged on the AIHEC Cyberinfrastructure Strategic Planning (CISP) Initiative, "Developing a technology roadmap at the TCUs to support their academic, research, business, and public service missions."

During this period we:

- Contributed to the development of a simple IT support assessment tool appropriate to the TCU community.
- Contributed to assessments at three TCUs, including regular meetings with TCU IT leadership, supporting the completion of their assessments, analysis of the resulting data, and initial work towards recommendations that will inform an IT strategic plan.
- Met with the AIHEC/CISP consultant team to share experiences and give them visibility into related efforts in the RCD community.

Outreach and communications

We provide annual reports of the community dataset, facilitate workshops and make presentations at PEARC conferences, conduct focus groups, etc. for working group activities, produce regular blog posts, e.g., [analyzing the time it takes different institutions to complete an RCD Capabilities Model assessment](#).

Office hours

As part of support for the RCD CM we have established regular office hours to provide support for institutions completing the Capabilities Model and for individuals needing more specific help. Discussions among individuals from participating institutions proved to be supportive and beneficial to both institutions and to the RCD CM Working Group with everything from approaches to campus participation to complete the survey, clarification on specific questions, and improvements for future versions of the Capabilities Model.

Office hours, from the start of the reporting period, have been held nine times with an average of six participants per session. Additional email follow-up addressed directly to working group members and to the capmodel-discuss@carcc.org mailing list have also resulted from office hours discussions.

Members of the RCD CM working group have also met individually with representatives from institutions requesting specific attention to their questions about the Model and the submission

process, as well as a discussion about strategies for engagement and best practices to complete the Model.

The RCD CM Working Group will continue to host regular office hours, generally staffed by two to four working group members at each session. They will continue to be provided remotely via Zoom and regularly advertised to the RCD CM participating institutions, general RCD community mailing lists, and the CaRCC and RCD Nexus websites and in relevant blog posts and newsletters.

4 RCD Staff Resources

RCD Nexus continues to develop Staff Resources to support RCD professionals and institutions that need research computing and data practitioners to support research activities. The key objectives are to address the challenges identified in a series of discussions, call for position papers and program experiences documentation, and a workshop.

These include:

- Identifying leading practices and common elements among staff workforce development programs
- Propagating various models to support workforce development for staff RCD practitioners (as well as undergraduate and graduate students in collaboration with the RCD Nexus Student Workforce workstream effort)
- Employing a “train the trainers” model to build a community of trainers that, in turn, helps educate other RCD professionals on workforce development topics

The materials gathered will provide the basis for an analysis to identify gaps and needs for additional training programs that would facilitate the transition from other positions into RCD roles, and, for example, developing existing RCD staff into RCD leadership roles. We have found, in order to accomplish this, we first must foster the RCD community to understand these efforts. Unlike some of the other work within the RCD Nexus, this effort is addressing newly identified needs, rather than continuing and growing efforts already underway.

Building a workforce development community

During the reporting period, we continued to grow a community of interested RCD professionals and provide opportunities for individuals to self-identify as participants in these workforce development efforts.

RCD Nexus Day: In July 2022, at the RCD Nexus Day, co-located with PEARC22, the Staff Workforce Development workstream held an all-day workshop whose outcomes included a set of priorities to guide the work we have been doing during this reporting period. Participants at

the workshop included 18 individuals, working in four groups to identify issues of interest including value proposition, KPI, ROI; tools and documentation; mentoring; and training.

Based on this input and the subsequent discussions, three top priorities were identified:

- Obtaining information about successful programs
- Learning about resources for mentor development
- Gathering ideas for establishing funding sustainability

New Staff Workforce Interest Group: With the support of the RCD Nexus steering committee and the growing number of interested individuals, we have established a CaRCC interest group that meets bi-monthly and is setting the foundation for gathering resource materials for RCD staff workforce development. The interest group has 60 members with diverse institutional representation.

Bi-monthly calls have included content and discussions relevant to the creation of RCD workforce resources that foster and reinforce RCD career development for those who support research and researchers. Content from the community calls included:

- North Carolina State University Research Facilitation Program lightning talk
- Review of the priorities developed during the RCD Nexus Day Staff Workforce Development workshop in July 2022
- Introduction of proposed working groups identified by the community: Onboarding, Training and Staff Development, Tools and Documentation, Mentoring and the standing committee on Gathering and Curating RCD Program Stories
- Update by the Career Arcs working group
- Presentation and small group breakout discussions and beginning documentation of RCD career phases (pre-, early-, mid-, and late-career definition, transition in and out of each phase, and the activities during each phase)

Presentations and small group breakout discussions have been recorded and one set of these documents is being used to develop a PEARC23 short paper on the phases of an RCD career, discussing the complexity of an RCD career and possible discrete phases, how one navigates into, out of, and within each phase. We expect this will be foundational to specific resources developed and provided through the RCD Nexus portal.

Curating Institutional Examples: We have established a standing committee that will gather and curate institutional RCD program stories, tag them for a set of characteristics in order to make them easy to search for and find, and create a foundation for eventual deposit into a repository in the RCD Nexus portal. We continue to work closely with the Student Workforce Development workstream. Because we recognize the areas of overlap, we alternate our monthly meeting time, and wherever it makes sense, we partner to move efforts forward. In particular, we have

kicked off a working group to address professional mentoring, including individual, student, and institutionally-led mentoring programs.

Additional working groups are being established and are set to kick-off, including those centered around staff onboarding, training and staff development, and tools and documentation supporting RCD staff.

5 Student Workforce Development

The focus of the Student RCD Workforce Development aspect of the project is to explore existing models for student RCD workforce development at both the undergraduate and graduate levels. Our main goal is to create a guide and other resources that share leading practices and models from organizations who are already doing this successfully. This team works in close coordination with the staff workforce development efforts.

In the current period, the RCD Student WD Interest Group was formally developed by the Student WD chairs (Hillary, Orendt, Cheatham) in conjunction with the RCD Staff Workforce Development Interest group chairs. The interest group was formally chartered. The group currently has 61 members. The chairs have aimed to meet every two weeks to plan activities with full interest group meetings and combined chairs meetings every month.

RCD Nexus Day workshop

To guide the activities of the Student Workforce Development interest group, a one-day workshop was held prior to PEARC22 in conjunction with RCD Nexus day. The workshop attracted 16 participants, including some of those who were not formally in the interest group. The meeting began with a brainstorming session during which attendees identified the need to gather information and case studies on existing student Workforce Development programs (what worked well and what did not, how to engage non-traditional domains and underrepresented communities, how to start a program, and how to recruit and retain students). Other critical topics included how to develop and train mentors, develop success metrics, explore sustainability and funding models, and secure leadership and institutional support for student workforce development.

The three priorities that emerged were:

- Finding successful student workforce development programs to serve as models
- Developing mentoring resources
- Identifying resources for funding and sustainability

Breakout sessions dug deeper into these themes and explored existing student workforce development programs in more detail. A product that emerged was a first draft of a questionnaire/survey about student workforce development programs at universities. After this event, three RCD Student Workforce Development calls have been held. They included presentations about student workforce development programs from Utah, Purdue, Texas A&M, and Northwestern as well as discussions on further survey development, a quick survey on student pay and discussions on student onboarding.

Onboarding programs

Onboarding will be the focus of a combined staff and student workforce development workshop at the next RCD nexus day prior to PEARC23. The RCD student workforce development interest group finalized a survey about student programs (IRB-exempt at University of Utah) that we released to the community on March 28, 2023. The survey remains open as this progress report is being written, with the expectation it will close in May 2023 and be analyzed by the interest group. So far, 15 responses have been submitted, discussing eight programs, including five with a longer description of their student program.

6 Job Family Matrix Adoption

RCD professionals have long pointed to the lack of an established job classification system as a barrier to recruitment, retention and advancement within the profession. An essential component of establishing equity across positions is having a job framework that corresponds to the complexity of the role and level of responsibility of positions, as well as up-to-date job descriptions that accurately reflect the regular tasks being performed. Without such a structure, it is difficult to reclassify positions and provide opportunities for promotion beyond a traditional management track, thus creating a glass ceiling for RCD professionals.

In Year 2, efforts continued to broadly distribute the RCD Job Family Matrix. Our dissemination efforts focused on adding information about the matrix to all CaRCC related presentations, including CaRCC Annual Retreat, RCD Nexus Day before PEARC22, and CASC 2022 fall meeting. We have also distributed information about the RCD Job Family Matrix through email lists including the CASC membership list, as it represents RCD directors from 90 institutions. To date there have been 301 total downloads from 251 unique emails across 153 different institutions, including 99 downloads from the past year. Of those from the past year, half were looking to implement the framework, showing there clearly remains an interest among RCD hiring managers to implement this framework in order to better support their staff and thus their institutional research mission.

Last year our plan was to host a workshop to:

- Share experiences from institutions that have already implemented the new HR Job Families
- Cultivate a cohort of subject matter experts (SMEs)
- Develop a guidebook for HR and hiring managers who are considering adoption of the RCD Job Family Matrix

However, we had to forgo our original plans, adapt, and make new ones based upon the feedback and availability we received. We continually hear that RCD managers want to implement the framework, but don't know where to begin and would like some consultation. However, their HR counterparts are reluctant to have an RCD professional from a specific institution provide direct consultation as they are concerned it might be biased (1) coming from RCD leadership and not HR, and (2) towards the institutional norms from their host institution. This is challenging because a number of institutions have hired outside consultants (either IT firms or HR firms) to perform the review of positions and help with classification, yet they have no context of what RCD professionals are and typically try to force positions into existing IT frameworks. Developing a cohort of subject matter experts and a brand for a future RCD Nexus (or CaRCC) consulting arm is work that should be addressed beyond this pilot.

Rather than hosting a workshop to develop a guidebook, we decided instead to hold a series of interviews and collaborative writing sessions. This gave us the advantage of working asynchronously with RCD hiring managers and not being limited to availability of these managers on a single date. The new format has also allowed for a more diverse participation. Six of these question and answer dialogues have been completed to date, with six more scheduled in May. In the upcoming months, we will compile the responses into a guidebook draft which all of the interview participants will help to edit. This guide book will be completed prior to PEARC23 in July, and we will submit our work as a panel discussion at PEARC23 to share our experiences with institutions interested in embarking on the process.

Thus far participants have included:

- Sean Cleveland, Associate Director of CI, University of Hawaii
- Craig Pohl, Director of Research Enterprise Services, Washington University of St. Louis
- Michael Navicky, Director HPC Collaboratory, Mississippi State University
- Lauren Michael, Director MSCI Consortium at Internet2, also representing her time at University of Wisconsin - Madison.
- Patrick Clemins, Manager of Cyberinfrastructure and Partnerships at Vermont EPSCoR, Vermont University
- Sarvani Chadalapaka, Director of Research Computing, University of California - Merced

Below we provide a synopsis of the Q & A sessions:

Q1: What were your goals in trying to implement the RCD HR Job Framework?

- Job titles that represent the depth and breadth of work being performed
- Enhance the ability for recruitment the right talent and retention of existing talent
- Proper compensation for the roles and responsibilities of staff
- Provide a pathway to advancement

Q2: Were you able to meet these goals? What did you accomplish with HR/Administration?

- Overall, the framework was well received by HR because the framework was viewed as a resource agreed-upon by a consortium of the peers. Everyone found it as a great resource to build out their own local model.
- It gave RC Managers/Directors “a leg up” compared to their IT peers when updating their job descriptions for positions that didn’t fit into prior classification frameworks.
- Using the framework provided a straightforward pathway to justify promotions of staff.

Q3: What challenges did you face in trying to implement this framework?

- HR didn’t want to completely adopt the framework, and found that RC Facilitators were unique, but that IT Infrastructure Engineers were close enough to RC Systems Engineers, and RSE was close enough to Software Engineer or Software Developers.
- Were able to demonstrate the need for more than two levels of individual contributor and one manager, however typically HR is still not comfortable with higher levels (4 & 5) of individual contributors, which are equivalent to manager roles.

Q4: What positive changes have been accomplished since your implementation?

- It improved staff’s recognition and compensation for the uniqueness of what RC Professionals do in comparison to their Enterprise IT or Research peers.
- Applicant pools for open positions are better aligned with job functions.
- It made it easier for HR to do compensation comparisons, which resulted in higher equity long-term.
- It made it much easier for RCD hiring managers to write new postings, with less time back and forth with HR.
- It Increased HR understanding of RCD and helped RCD hiring managers build rapport with HR.
- In organizations with prior flat HR structures, where everyone did everything, it focused staff’s efforts on their specific roles, which created better division of labor.

Q5: Were there any unanticipated negative consequences?

- Finding the funding to support promotion that was well justified by HR
- Implementation of position alignment largely left to local managers to decide might not be the most rigorous way to accomplish implementation

Q6: What suggestions would you give to others working with HR & Administration in adopting this framework?

- It's not going to be perfect – nothing is. But it's a good place to start. You have to have the conversations with HR and create a job matrix for your local organization and then think about how it fits into the larger organization.
- Provide the facts and history about this framework's creation, which will help HR view this as the “authoritative framework” vetted by a number of prominent organizations.
- Be sure to leverage that other leading institutions used this framework and made this transition already will help HR listen, but remember, working with HR is going to be unique to every institution.
- This work to update positions will be an ongoing process and it's not quick. Transitions across a whole unit will take a while, there is a lot of inertia in the old system, so don't lose patience.

7 RCD Workforce Survey

As noted in the prior report on-going work from the 2021 survey of RCD Professionals would continue. The focus this year was to (1) publish a public data resource and (2) publish a paper that focused on compensation.

As mentioned previously, Christina Maimone, Northwestern University is PI of the IRB study, and she took the lead on publishing the public datasets. The datasets are split and the set of variables is restricted to protect the privacy of survey respondents. The public data set includes a readme file explaining all of the files, the csv data files, and the R code used to generate the figures. Twenty-six visualizations were created and posted on the RCD Nexus data portal⁵, covering the following themes: demographics, education, work experience, current positions, and experience within the RCD field and position. These figures supplement the tables that were in the PEARC22 paper, as space was limited. These visualizations provide easy access to others that need a definitive source of data to support the various slices of demographics that make up the RCD profession.

In order to better understand the characteristics of RCD compensation, the 2021 survey of RCD professionals in the United States gathered salary information from 477 RCD professionals,

⁵ <https://rcd-nexus.org/data/rcd-workforce-data/>

including 393 respondents working at non-medical academic institutions. Ashley Stauffer of Penn State University took the lead in organizing the group to build a narrative with the compensation data. She was also able to recruit some new participation in this working group. This has resulted in the acceptance of a PEARC23 paper (referenced in Sec. 10 below). A synopsis of the work can be distilled into the following statement: “The median salary reported for academic institutions was \$90,000 (\$80,000 for individual contributor levels), with variation observed across respondents’ position levels, gender, ethnicity, education, years of experience, and geography. While RCD roles require a combination of expertise in two fields — research and technology — the median compensation for academic RCD professionals falls below that for either of these fields independently.” One of the challenges faced in creating the discussion is that there are few publicly available compensation studies that make sense with which to compare. The closest comparisons are with purely academic surveys that mostly include faculty compensation and tech industry compensation, which are highly elevated positions like data engineers and data scientists. To make this resource more useful to HR and hiring managers we need a cost of living adjustment as applied to the various levels of positions. However, we simply didn’t have enough participation from individuals from geographical centers to publish this data set without individuals being represented, and thus identifiable. A much larger participation (2000-3000) in the survey would be needed to accomplish this goal.

8 Program Administration

RCD Nexus consists of a set of related but distinct projects or workstreams, each managed by one of the Principal Investigators (PIs). The RCD Nexus team members also serve in various roles across CaRCC including the Logistics and Engagement Operations groups, the People Network Strategy and Policy-facing track, in addition to the roles in these workstreams as co-chairs of the RCD Capabilities Model, RCD Professionalization, RCD Career Arcs, and RCD Staff and Student workforce groups.

In order to keep all these work areas in sync and to enable identification of cross-project risks and opportunities, we conducted a series of program administration activities during the reporting period, including:

- Coordinated the May 2022 CaRCC Annual meeting with participation from RCD Nexus and CaRCC Advisory Committees, CaRCC chairs, People Network Coordinators, and several individuals from adjacent RCD Communities
- Held the first annual RCD Nexus Day co-located with PEARC22
- Lead and Contributed to CaRCC Chairs Monthly meetings
- Contributed to CaRCC Logistics Operations group (Brunson is co-chair, Schmitz, Cheatham, and McCanse are members).

- Contributed to CaRCC Engagement Operations Group (Mizumoto is co-chair, Cheatham and McCause are members)
- Managed project and engagement planning activities which reflect plans and progress against milestones
- Liaised with key collaborators and other community organization and project leads in order to establish and solidify partnerships (e.g., Brunson serves on external advisory boards for NSF ACCESS, NSF Chase-CI, Cloudbank, Nevada’s NSF EPSCoR track 1 Harnessing the Data Revolution for Fire Science, etc)
- Managed sub-award contracts and oversaw spending
- Established program templates, policies, and procedures
- Posted presentations and other resources to the website and Zonodo for community use. (See section 10.)
- Disseminated program news and upcoming event information (see section 2)

9 Looking Forward

The work of RCD Nexus and CaRCC is driven and executed by a large cadre of volunteers (see Committees and Working groups below.) RCD Nexus support has provided much needed infrastructure and support in every aspect of CaRCC, which has amplified the impact of these volunteers, but it falls short of the overall needs, hampering progress on important priorities. There has been a significant increased need for coordination, facilitation, outreach, and communication within working groups, across the organization, and more broadly.

The growth and the reputation of CaRCC and RCD Nexus for delivering results has led to an increase in requests for additional support (e.g., consulting, training, and communications) and new resources (e.g., gathering and curating leading practices in RCD, job board, and help with hiring). This growth has also led to an increased need for core resources that enable and coordinate the volunteers who are eager to participate and to reach out to more communities to broaden the representation within CaRCC.

Over the next year (via our no cost extension), we will continue progressing on the elements as described in the previous sections and continue developing the vision for CaRCC in support of the broad RCD Communities.

The next phase priorities for RCD Nexus (through the remaining pilot project and beyond) are:

- Refine and grow the CaRCC organization and enabling infrastructure to accelerate emerging RCD activities and increase their impact
- Expand our work in core areas of tools, leading practices, and curated training resources, and ensure these are highly visible and accessible

- Engage related programs (Virtual Residency, CI leadership academy, CyberAmbassadors, etc.) to expand their visibility, reach, and impact
- Build out the RCD Career Center to help job-seekers advance their careers and help hiring managers to build and grow their teams.
- Provide expert consulting and training services
- Coordinate the development of a model for an RCD Professional Society

And our long term goals include:

- Ensure CaRCC has the necessary resources and services to fully support the expanding community activities that address the needs of RCD Professionals and advance research
- Accelerate the development of practical, high-visibility outcomes from CaRCC working groups
- Promote the continued growth of the CaRCC community and coordinate the establishment of a professional society
- Make concrete progress on key challenges in hiring, training, and advancing the careers of people in RCD professional roles
- Promote a clear understanding of RCD professional roles and their impact across the research community

10 Publications and Presentations

Publications

Shafaq Chaudhry, Arman Pazouki, Patrick Schmitz, Elizabeth Hillery, and Kerk Kee. 2022. Understanding Factors that Influence Research Computing and Data Careers. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '22). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 25, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491418.3530292>

Joel Cutcher-Gershenfeld, Torey Battelle, Dana Brunson, Thomas Cheatham, Jacob Fosso Tande, Douglas M. Jennewein, Julie Ma, Lauren A. Michael, Timothy Middelkoop, Henry Neeman, and Christina Maimone, Carrie Brown, Kimberly Grasch, Chris Reidy, and Ashley Stauffer. 2023. Compensation of Academic Research Computing and Data Professionals. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '23), July 23–27, 2023, Portland, OR, USA. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 12 pages. (to appear)

Thomas Hacker, Preston Smith, Dana Brunson, Lisa Arafune, Thomas Cheatham, and Ewa Deelman. 2022. Building the Research Innovation Workforce: Challenges and Recommendations from a Virtual Workshop to Advance the Research Computing Community. In Practice and

Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '22). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 26, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491418.3530288>

Christina Maimone, Scott Yockel, Jay Alameda, Timothy Middelkoop, Amy Neeser, and Asheley Stauffer. 2022. CaRCC Research Computing and Data (RCD) Workforce Survey Data 2021 - Part 1 (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6574465>

Christina Maimone, Scott Yockel, Timothy Middelkoop, Ashley Stauffer, and Chris Reidy. 2022. Characterizing the US Research Computing and Data (RCD) Workforce. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '22). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 27, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491418.3530289>

Patrick Schmitz. 2023. Professionalization of Research Computing and Data: An Expanded Agenda. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '23), July 23–27, 2023, Portland, OR, USA. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 12 pages. (to appear)

Patrick Schmitz, Venice Bayrd, Scotty Strachan, and Gwen Jacobs. 2022. A Baseline of EPSCoR Research CI Capabilities. RCD Nexus Technical Report. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6395204>

Presentations (listed chronologically)

John Hicks and Patrick Schmitz, “RCD Capabilities Model Essentials version Focus Group,” in collaboration with NJEdge, April 8, 2022

John Hicks and Patrick Schmitz, “RCD Capabilities Model Essentials version Focus Group,” in collaboration with Great Plains Network, April 29, 2022

John Hicks, “CaRCC Capabilities Model Essentials Version Discussion” at the Great Plains Network Annual Meeting, Kansas City, June 2, 2022.

Timothy Middelkoop, “Results of the 2021 RCD Census Survey,” at the Great Plains Network Annual Meeting, June 3, 2022.

Dana Brunson & Timothy Middelkoop, “The Cyberinfrastructure Landscape: Organizations”, at the University of Oklahoma led Virtual Residency Workshop (virtual), June 30, 2022.

Venice Bayrd, Dana Brunson, Thomas Cheatham, Bob Freeman, Gwen Jacobs, Christina Maimone, Ruth Marinshaw, Lauren Michael, Claire Mizumoto, Arman Pazouki, Patrick Schmitz and Scott Yockel, “CaRCC Town Hall” at PEARC '22, July 12, 2022, Boston, MA

Shafaq Chaudhry, Arman Pazouki, Patrick Schmitz, Elizabett Hillery, and Kerk Kee. 2022. Understanding Factors that Influence Research Computing and Data Careers. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '22). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 25, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491418.3530292>

Thomas Hacker, Preston Smith, Dana Brunson, Lisa Arafune, Thomas Cheatham, and Ewa Deelman. 2022. Building the Research Innovation Workforce: Challenges and Recommendations from a Virtual Workshop to Advance the Research Computing Community. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '22). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 26, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491418.3530288>

Christina Maimone, Scott Yockel, Timothy Middelkoop, Ashley Stauffer, and Chris Reidy. 2022. Characterizing the US Research Computing and Data (RCD) Workforce. In Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '22). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 27, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491418.3530289>

Shafaq Chaudhry, Arman Pazouki, Patrick Schmitz, Elizabett Hillery, and Kerk Kee. (2022, Sept 14). “Understanding Factors that Influence Research Computing and Data Careers.” RSE Virtual Workshop

Timothy Middelkoop, Dana Brunson, and Lauren Michael. (2022, December 6). “How Can We Advance the RCD Profession?” at Internet2 Technology Exchange 2022. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7504842>

Scott Yockel, “Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC) Cross-Consortium DEIA Efforts,” Presentation to the Coalition for Academic Scientific Computation (CASC) Fall 2022 Meeting, October 18-20, 2022

Venice Bayrd, Dana Brunson, Thomas Cheatham, Bob Freeman, Ruth Marinshaw, Lauren Michael, Claire Mizumoto, Patrick Schmitz, Scott Yockel, “CaRCC Parade,” CaRCC People Network plenary session, Jan 24, 2023.

Workshops (listed chronologically)

Venice Bayrd, Gwen Jacobs, Patrick Schmitz and Scotty Strachan, “Research CI in EPSCoR Jurisdictions: Assessment, Planning, & Partnerships” at the EPSCoR CI Spring Preliminary Workshop March 10 & 17, 2022

CaRCC Spring 2022 Planning workshop, May 10-11, 2022, Denver, CO.

Patrick Schmitz, Claire Mizumoto, Dana Brunson, Douglas Jennewein, Galen Collier, and John Hicks. 2022.. Building and Selling a Strategic Plan for your Research Computing and Data Program. Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC '22) (PEARC22). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7600430>

Patrick Schmitz, John Hicks, Dana Brunson, James Deaton, and Forough Ghahramani, “Defining an RCD Capabilities Model Essentials version,” Workshop at the 2022 RCD Nexus Day, Jul 10th, 2022

Claire Mizumoto, Timothy Middelkoop, “RCD Staff Workforce Development: Identifying and Addressing Challenges and Opportunities for RCD Professionals,” Workshop at the 2022 RCD Nexus Day, July 10, 2022

Elizabeth Hillery, Anita Orendt, “RCD Student Workforce Development: RCD Student Programs Exploration” Workshop at the 2022 RCD Nexus Day, July 10, 2022

Gwen Jacobs, Venice Bayrd, Scotty Strachan, Patrick Schmitz and Claire Mizumoto, “Research Cyberinfrastructure within NSF-EPSCoR Assessment, Planning, & Partnerships” A Research CI Workshop at the 27th NSF EPSCoR National Conference (November 13th, 2022)

People Network sessions - Recordings available on YouTube ([link](#))

Data Facing Track:

Joint Call with Researcher Track – Harvard Data Commons (February 16, 2023)

Round Robin Session (January 3, 2023)

The ICPSR Research Data Ecosystem (November 1, 2022)

Panel on Teaching Research Data Management to Students (October 4, 2022)

Cardiac Arrest Registry to Enhance Survival: Data Collection, Research and Outreach discussion (Sept 6, 2022)

Standards and terminologies for health data: a (brief) introduction to common data elements, common data models, and terminologies (July 5, 2022)

Background and Demonstration of the Open Research Toolkit, an OER for Learning about the Open Research Ecosystem (May 3, 2022)

Emerging Centers Track:

National Resources Series: ACCESS Allocations (4/19/2023)

FAIR Principles and Storage (3/15/2023)

The New NIH Data Management and Sharing Policy (2/23/2023)

The Business of HPC Centers: The Good, The Bad, and the Ugly (12/14/2022)

The Cultural Fit between Research and Enterprise IT (10/19/2022)

Metrics for RCD Success (9/21/2022)

Specialization and Silos (8/17/2022)

Looking forward: future topic discussion (6/15/2022)

Meet the Strategy and Policy-Facing Track (5/18/2022)

Researcher-Facing Track:

STRIDES, Cloud Service Program at The National Institute of Health (3/9/2023)

ACCESS Support Empowers Your Needs (2/8/2023)

What's hot in 2023? (1/12/2023)

Intellectual Property and Technology Transfer (11/10/2022)

Research data storage (10/13/2022)

Inter-institutional collaboration (9/8/2022)

Highlights from PEARC22 (8/11/2022)

Supporting researchers with the NIH Data Management and Sharing Plan Requirement (6/9/2022)

Strategy and Policy-Facing Track:

Origin stories of RCD programs (4/5/2023)

Exploring factors that impact RCD strategy (part 2). (3/1/2023)

Exploring factors that impact RCD strategy. (2/1/2023)

Updates from CASC, EDUCAUSE, NSF Cybersecurity Summit. (12/2/2022)

Systems-Facing Track:

Deploying web-based software to enable self-service HPC for researchers on the commercial cloud (January 2023)

Identifying "core/common skills" that a Novice RCD Systems Focused IT professional should prioritize developing as they start their career. – Part 2 (October 2022)

Open XDMoD/ColdFront/Open OnDemand HPC Toolset Overview (September 2022)

Identifying Requirements for Early Career PT/FT RCD Systems Focused IT – Part 1 (August 2022)

JupyterHub @ NCAR: A Case for a Notebook-Centric Analysis Platform Around the Jupyter Ecosystem (June 2022)

Operating a research computing environment for a large university (May 2022)

11 Committees and Working Groups

RCD Nexus Advisory Committee

Linda Akli, Southeastern Universities Research Association
Ewa Deelman, University of Southern California
Joel Cutcher-Gershenfeld, Brandeis University
Sandra Gesing, University of Illinois, Chicago
John Goodhue, Massachusetts Green High Performance Computing Center
Leah Lang, EDUCAUSE (withdrew due to change of position)
Jackie Milhans, Northwestern University
John Towns, University of Illinois
Von Welch, Indiana University (withdrew due to retirement)

CaRCC Advisory Committee

Amy Neeser, UC Berkeley
Ana Hunsinger, Internet2
Ann Kovalchick, UC Merced
Ashley Stauffer, Penn State University
Dan Stanzione, TACC/UT Austin
Danielle Cooper, Ithaka S&R
Erik Lundberg, U Washington
Henry Neeman, University of Oklahoma
Jackie Milhans, Northwestern (co-chair)
Jim Bottum (co-chair)
Linda Akli, SURA/XSEDE
Susan Mehringer, Cornell University

CaRCC Chairs Leadership

Venice Bayrd, Montana State (EPSCoR CI Workshop)
Dana Brunson, Internet2 (RCD Capabilities Model; Logistics)
Thomas Cheatham, University of Utah (Decadal Survey; RCD Student Workforce Development)
Bob Freeman, Harvard Business School (People Network; Logistics)
Betsy Hillery, Purdue University (RCD Student Workforce Development)
Gwen Jacobs, University of Hawaii (EPSCoR CI Workshop)
Julie Ma, Massachusetts Green High Performance Computing Center (Engagement)
Christina Maimone, Northwestern University (RCD Professionalization)
Ruth Marinshaw, Stanford University (Decadal Survey)
Lauren Michael, Internet2 (Logistics; People Network)

Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2 (RCD Staff Workforce Development)
Claire Mizumoto, University of California, San Diego (Engagement; RCD Staff Workforce Dev)
Anita Orendt, University of Utah (RCD Student Workforce Development)
Arman Pazouki, Northwestern University (Career Arcs)
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito Consulting (RCD Capabilities Model; Career Arcs; Logistics)
Scott Yockel, Harvard University (RCD Professionalization)

Capabilities Model Working Group

Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito (co-chair)
Dana Brunson, Internet2 (co-chair)
Claire Mizumoto, UC San Diego (past co-chair)
Thomas Cheatham, University of Utah
Galen Collier, Rutgers University
John Hicks, Internet2
Douglas Jennewein, Arizona State University
Scotty Strachan, Nevada
James Deaton, Internet2
Forough Ghahramani, NJEdge
Lauren Michael, MS-CC
Paul Fischer, U of Utah
Don DuRousseau, University of Arkansas

Focused Tools Committee:

John Hicks, Internet2 (co-chair)
Forough Ghahramani, NJEdge (co-chair)
Paul Arias, Rutgers University
Kirk Anne, Rochester Institute of Technology
Izzat Alsmadi, Texas A&M
Shu Wan, University of Buffalo
Rick Tuthill, University of Massachusetts
Rick McMullen, Retired
Andy Sherman, Yale
Robert Henschel
Chuntida Harinnitisuk, UT Health - San Antonio
Stefan Robila, Montclair State University
Don DuRousseau, University of Arkansas
Mike Austin, University of Vermont
Widodo Samyono, Jarvis Christian University
Bala Desinghu, Rutgers University
James Deaton, Internet2

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Claire Mizumoto, UC San Diego

RCD Professionalization Working Group

Christina Maimone, Northwestern University (exiting co-chair)
Ashley Stauffer, Penn State University (incoming co-chair)
Scott Yockel, Harvard University (co-chair)
Kimberly Grasch, University of Chicago
Tim Middelkoop, Internet2
Chris Reidy, University of Arizona
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito
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Susan Ivy, North Carolina State University
Nicole Klueber, Penn State University

RCD Career Arcs Working Group

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Arman Pazouki, Purdue (past co-chair)
Betsy Hillery, Purdue
Shafaq Chaudhry, U. of Central Florida
Gladys Andino, U Virginia
Kerk Kee, Texas Tech
Laura Carriere, NASA
Preston Smith, Purdue
Sarvani Chadalapaka, UC Merced

EPSCoR CI Workshop Working Group

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Venice Bayrd, Montana State (co-Chair)
Fred Harris, UN Reno
Dana Brunson, Internet2
Scotty Strachan, Nevada System of Higher Education
Pips Veazey, U Maine

Deborah Dent, Jackson State
Doug Jennewein, ASU
Patrick Schmitz, Semper Cogito
Bill Michener, U New Mexico
Tara Borland, University of Alaska
Zach Byerly, Louisiana State University
Patrick Clemins, University of Vermont

RCD Staff Workforce Development Interest Group

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Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2 (co-chair)
Thomas Cheatham, University of Utah
Anita Orendt, University of Utah
Kathryn Kelley, CASC
Matt Lacy, Texas A&M
Christopher Simmons, Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Mego Franks, Wake Forest School of Medicine
Matthew Keeler, University of Missouri System
Arman Pazouki, Purdue
Tom Gulbransen, NSF
Amy Nurnberger, Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Forough Ghahramani, NJEdge
Joshua Baller, University of Minnesota
Sandy Shew, The Ohio State University
Gladys Andino, University of Virginia
Amy Neeser, Berkeley
Grace Faustino, University of New Mexico
Henry Neeman, University of Oklahoma-Norman
Janna Nugent, Northwestern University
Jill Gemmill, Clemson
Shuai Liu, University of arkansas
Mary Murphy, University of Wisconsin-Madison
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Berhane Temelso, George Mason University
Jayshree Sarma, George Mason University

Swabir Silayi, George Mason University
Jose Martinez, UCLA
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